

Lead City Journal of the Social Sciences (LCJSS)

**Faculty of Management and Social Sciences
Lead City University, Ibadan**

**ISSN: 2449092X
Volume 10 (No. 3) / December 2025**

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Sowunmi Emmanuel Olatubosun and Olukotun Omolola Helen

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Philip Olugbemiga Oyedapo

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Aremu Atinuke Bukola and Egunjobi Grace Oyejope

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Mohammed Lawal Inuwa, Friday Igbadumhe Abaye, and Hashim Sabo Bello

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Faculty of Management and Social Sciences

Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

www.lcu.edu.ng/index.php/lead-city-journal-of-the-social-sciences

e-mail: (i) editor.lcjss@gmail.com

(ii) campbell.omolara@lcu.edu.ng

(iii) omolaracampbell@yahoo.com
+2348033176177, +2348033234042

Published by

Lead City University, Press

Beside Methodist School, Toll-Gate Area, Lagos-Ibadan Express Way, Ibadan

07064671658, 08036694838

lcupress23@gmail.com

Lead City Journal of the Social Sciences (LCISS) ISSN: 2449092X

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Contents

Investing in Human Capital as a Driver of Economic Growth in Nigeria <i>Sowunmi Emmanuel Olatubosun and Olukotun Omolola Helen</i>	8
Evaluating the Impact of Students' Attitudes on Waste Management in Federal Colleges of Education, Southwest Nigeria <i>Oreagba Oluwakemi Taiwo and Azeez Sherifat Abiodun</i>	25
Trade Liberalization and Economic Growth in Sub-Saharan African Countries <i>Aderoju Bolanle Rahmon and Campbell Omolara Ayotunde</i>	38
The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Strategic Human Resource Management: A Case of the Banking Sector in Ibadan, Nigeria <i>Aremu Atinuke Bukola, Aikulola, Emmanuel Abiodun, and Egunjobi, Grace Oyejope</i>	55
The Role of Traditional Institutions in Conflict Resolution and their Impact on Grassroots Development: A Study of Selected Communities in Osun State, Nigeria <i>Olawoyin Mustapha Adeyemi and Badru Ronald Olufemi</i>	67
Corporate Social Responsibility and Human Capital Development: A Study of MTN Nigeria's Initiatives <i>Philip Olugbemiga Oyedapo</i>	81
Acquisition of Digital Skills and Its Impact on Unemployment Reduction among Nigerian Youth <i>Aremu Atinuke Bukola and Egunjobi Grace Oyejope</i>	96
Digital Marketing, Human Capital and Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) in Northeast Nigeria: A Conceptual Review <i>Mohammed Lawal Inuwa, Friday Igbadumhe Abaye, and Hashim Sabo Bello</i>	116
Enhancing Electoral Processes through E-governance: Opportunities and Challenges in Nigeria <i>Jeleel Abioye Ahmed and Fausat Remilekun Sarumi</i>	131
Preventive Maintenance, and Customer Satisfaction in Selected Hotels in Ibadan. <i>Opatola, Grace Nike and Balogun, Khidir Bolaji</i>	143

Tax Policy Implementation, Information Technology, and Performance of the State Internal Revenue Service (SIRS) in Southwest Nigeria

Yusuf Alabi Olumoh, Mubaraq Sanni and Abdulrasaq Mustapha 153

Artificial Intelligence and Human Capital Development in Nigeria

Tosin Araromi Maryanne 181

Promoting Inclusive Education for Children with Disabilities in Ibadan Metropolis: The Role of Community-Based Social Work

Oluwadamilare Jesuferanmi Elijah 192

Trade Liberalization and Economic Growth in Sub-Saharan African Countries

Aderoju, Bolanle Rahmon

Department of Economics

School of Arts and Social Sciences

Oyo State College of Education, Lanlate

&

Campbell Omolara Ayotunde

Department of Economics and Development Studies

Faculty of Management and Social Sciences

Lead City University, Ibadan

Abstract

This study empirically examined the effect of trade liberalization on economic growth in Sub-Saharan African countries over the period 2000 to 2022 using panel data obtained from World Development Indicator (WDI) database. Pooled Ordinary Least Square (POLLS), Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and Two-Step Difference Generalized Method of Moments (TSDGMM) were the estimating techniques employed in analyzing the data. Empirical findings from the study revealed that trade liberalization (TLIB) had a statistically significant positive relationship with economic growth in Sub-Saharan African countries. The results further showed that net foreign direct investment (NFDI), total population (TPOP) and inflation rate (INFR) had statistically significant positive relationships with economic growth while gross fixed capital formation (GCF) and labour force (LABF) exerted statistically significant negative contributions to economic growth of SSA countries. Based on the estimated results, governments of Sub-Saharan African countries should strengthen their domestic institutions, particularly those related to governance and contract enforcement; and there should be massive investment in infrastructure and human capital development to support trade and enhance overall economic performance. In addition, implementation of complementary policies that address potential challenges and enhance the benefits of trade liberalization must be vigorously pursued.

Keywords: Trade liberalization, Economic growth, pooled ordinary least squares, fixed effect model, Two-step difference GMM, Sub-Saharan Africa

Introduction

Trade liberalization is germane to the global economy because of its ability to increase economic growth by providing access to commodities and services, improving resource allocation effectiveness, and boosting total factor productivity through the spread of knowledge and technological advancement. The Classical and Neo-classical economists attributed great importance to international trade in a region's development that they considered it as an 'engine

of growth'. International trade increases savings and investments, advances technological capacity, reduces unemployment and under-employment, facilitates greater backward and forward linkages in the economy and ensures a larger inflow of factor inputs into the economy and outflow of goods and services. Trade liberalization has been defined as the elimination or reduction of tariff and non-tariff barriers created by government policies, regulations and administrative procedures that hamper the free flow of goods, services and capital across national borders and is generally regarded as the major driving force behind globalization. Since 1980s, several international organizations such as International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Bank (WB), World Trade Organization (WTO) and Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) have been persuading Sub-Saharan African countries to liberalize their trade policies to accelerate their rates of economic growth. The idea put forward by these international organizations is that nations that permit higher level of trade liberalization policies outperform countries with tighter international trade policies.

The proponents of trade liberalization argued that it has numerous benefits which include exposure to global competition, advancement in technological capacity, facilitation of knowledge transfer, increase in world living standard, creation of marketing networks, reduction of global cost of living, improvement in consumers' welfare, attraction of foreign direct investment, reduction of monopoly power of the public sector, creation of employment opportunities, reduction in rates of interest and tariffs, availability and affordability of global inputs and enhancement of economic growth. The impressive economic success of the South-East Asian countries (Taiwan, South Korea, Singapore and Hong-Kong) corroborated the view among international organizations that such a development strategy is both effective and desirable. Trading activities traceable to trade liberalization usually include exports, imports, foreign direct investment, lending, borrowing and repatriation of funds from abroad.

In Sub-Saharan African countries, trade liberalization is characterized by a general move towards more open trade regimes, though the specific policies and their impacts vary. While many countries in the region initially had restrictive trade regimes, they have been largely successful in implementing significant trade reforms, aiming to reduce restrictiveness. These reforms often involved reducing tariffs and other trade barriers, and in some cases, liberalizing exchange rate regimes. Among the prominent features of world economy in the last three decades was that developing economies, especially Sub-Saharan Africa countries, went through fast trade liberalization either individually or as a component of multilateral proposals with the World Bank (WB), World Trade Organization (WTO) and the International Monetary Fund (IMF). Hence, in the early 1980s, most countries in Sub-Saharan Africa effected numerous trade reforms besides the Structural Adjustment Programs (SAPs) imposed by international trade and financial organizations as a necessary step for a free market economy. These include trade liberalization, private sector development via reduction in administrative barriers to trade and investment, legal and judicial reform to increase economic

security, and financial sector reform to develop money markets and indirect instruments of monetary policy, reduction of opportunities for corruption, encouragement of openness and transparency of government, creation of conducive environment for private sector investment and production. All these measures are expected to enhance productivity and competitiveness of the SSA region's products in relation to the rest of the world. The unprecedented integration of the economies of the SSA countries to the economies of the rest of the world is expected to spur regional economic growth.

Economic growth is defined as an increase in the quantity and quality of the economic goods and services that a society produces. It also refers to an increase in the size of a country's economy over a period. The size of an economy is typically measured by the total production of goods and services in the economy, which is called gross domestic product. Sub-Saharan Africa's economic growth is characterized by significant fluctuations and varying growth rates among countries. While the region has witnessed periods of strong growth, it has also faced challenges like declining growth rates, periods of stagnation, and a dependence on a few key sectors. Many SSA countries heavily rely on natural resources, especially oil and minerals, for export revenue. This can lead to vulnerability to price shocks and limit diversification of the economy. Agriculture plays a notable role in many SSA countries, but it also encounters challenges like low productivity, climate change impacts, and a reliance on traditional farming methods. The region's predicaments to sustained growth include resource dependence, huge infrastructure deficits, high population growth, inadequate human capital, regional inequality, limited structural transformation, external shocks, institutional weaknesses and political instability.

Although the relationship between trade liberalization and economic growth has been analyzed extensively both in advanced and developing economies in recent decades, it remains a controversial topic among policymakers and economists because of the diversity in the empirical findings. It is worth mentioning that existing studies conducted on the effect of trade liberalization policies on economic growth in Sub-Saharan African are mostly country-specific and scanty (Khobai & Chitauro, 2020; Umoh & Onye, 2020; Mahfoudh & Aleisa, 2020). Since almost all Sub-Saharan African countries have liberalized their trade policies with a view to accelerating their rates of economic growth over the past few decades, it becomes imperative to investigate in empirical terms the impact of trade liberalization on their rates of economic growth. Although, there are plethora of studies on the impact of trade liberalization on economic growth at country specific level in SSA countries. To the best of the researchers' knowledge, only few studies have investigated the relationship between trade liberalization and economic growth for Sub-Saharan African countries. It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to examine the influence of trade liberalization policies on economic growth of Sub-Saharan African countries between 2000 and 2022. The newness or originality of this study

can be seen in terms of its methodology, large sample size and carefully chosen control variables.

Theoretical Literature Review

This study is based on three theories that account for the gains of trade liberalization to countries. These are the comparative advantage theory propounded by David Ricardo, Heckscher-Ohlin neoclassical factor endowment theory of trade and the endogenous growth theory. Comparative advantage theory states that countries engaging in international trade should specialize in the production and exportation of goods and services where they have comparative advantages. A country is said to have comparative advantage in the production of a particular good or service if it can produce the good or service at a lower opportunity cost than its trading partners. Comparative advantage refers to the products that a country can produce more cheaply than other countries. This theory can also be regarded as the best option given trade-off. The right of entry to export markets is increased through international trade, and economies would benefit if increasing returns to scale are presumed to hold. These benefits from trade could accrue to the SSA economies under the platform of trade liberalization through the enhanced right of entry to international markets.

The Heckscher-Ohlin's theory of factor endowment is another form of comparative advantage theory in international trade postulated by two Swedish Economists in 1933³. The theory states that countries engaging in international trade should specialize in the production and exportation of products based on the availability of productive resources or factors endowment. According to the proponents of the theory, countries in which capital is relatively plentiful or abundant and labour relatively scarce will tend to produce and export capital-intensive products and import labour-intensive products, while countries in which labour is relatively plentiful and capital relatively scarce will tend to produce and export intensive products and import capital intensive products. For example, goods requiring much capital and only a little labour such as automobiles and chemicals tend to be relatively inexpensive in countries with plentiful and cheap capital. Thus, countries with abundant capital should generally be able to produce capital-intensive goods relatively inexpensively, exporting them in order to pay for imports of labour-intensive goods.

The endogenous growth theory postulates that growth results from domestic factors in an economy such as innovation, population growth, knowledge and investment in human capital. Endogenous growth theory states that economic growth in any country is primarily the result of internal forces, rather than external ones. The theory maintains that investment in human capital, population growth, innovation and knowledge are significant contributors to economic growth. It also focuses on positive externalities and spillover effects of a knowledge-based economy which will lead to economic development. The endogenous growth theory

primarily holds that the enhancement of a nation's human capital will lead to economic growth by means of development of new forms of technology and effective means of production.

Empirical Literature Review

Numerous studies have been conducted in both advanced and developing economies of the world to investigate the relationship between trade liberalization and economic growth. Some of these studies are reviewed below. Augustine & Abieyuwa (2024) empirically investigated the impact of trade liberalization on economic growth in South Africa covering the period of 1986 to 2022. Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) was the estimating technique employed to find the parameters of the model. Empirical findings revealed that there exists a positive relation between trade liberalization and economic growth in South Africa. The study recommended that the African governments especially South Africa should further open its economic border to allow for free trade with other economies of the world. Ifarajimi & Ajaegbu (2024) examined the effect of trade liberalization on long run economic growth in Nigeria spanning from 2000 to 2021. Annual time series data obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria's Statistical Bulletin (CBNSB) and World Bank Development Indicators (WBDI) were utilized for the study. The model specification had economic growth measured by gross domestic product as the dependent variable while gross fixed capital formation, trade liberalization, labour force participation rate, inflation and interest rates were the independent variables of interest. Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test, Johansen cointegration test and linear regression model were employed in determining the parameters of the study. Empirical findings revealed that trade liberalization and gross fixed capital formation have a positive and significant effect on economic growth. In addition, inflation and interest rates were shown to have a negative influence on economic growth whereas labour force participation rate was found to have a positive impact on economic growth. The study recommended that the government should implement suitable policies to diversify the productive base of the economy in order to encourage net exports, as well as construct an efficient service infrastructure to stimulate private domestic and international investment.

Chukwu & Jepkorir (2024) empirically examined the effect of trade liberalization on economic growth in Kenya spanning 1990 to 2022. Annual time series data sourced from World Bank Development Indicators (WBDI) were utilized for the study. Vector Auto regression (VAR) was employed in determining the parameters of the study. Empirical results showed that foreign direct investments inflows exerted a statistically significant negative effect on economic growth while manufacturing output had a statistically significant positive effect on economic growth in Kenya. The study recommended that Kenyan policymakers should control ways to draw in beneficial FDI while simultaneously emphasizing the manufacturing sector which will be beneficial for the economy.

Ita et al. (2024) investigated empirically the nexus between trade liberalization and economic growth in Nigeria from the period 1981 to 2021. Annual time series data gathered from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) were used for the study. The study employed the econometrics method of Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL), Error Correction Model (ECM) and Toda-Yamamoto Causality (TYC) test in estimating the parameters of the study. Empirical results indicated that export value index proxy for exports had a statistically significant positive relationship with the growth rate of gross domestic product in the long run, import value index proxy for imports impacted a statistically significant negative relationship with growth rate of gross domestic product in the long run. Moreover, trade openness and exchange rate had a significant negative relationship with growth rate of gross domestic product in the long run. The paper, therefore, recommended that trade policies by ministry of trade and industry should be targeted at encouraging Nigerian businesses to diversify their export products and markets beyond traditional commodities, promote value-added manufacturing, agricultural processing, and service exports to increase the range of exportable goods and services.

Manyela & Charles (2024) empirically assessed the interplay between trade liberalization, economic growth and economic development for two distinct periods, pre-BRICS (1991-2010) and post-BRICS (2011-2021) in South Africa. A Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) was employed to account for potential cointegration among the variables. Empirical findings revealed that there exists a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables. The estimated results indicated that trade openness positively and substantially influenced gross domestic product growth rate in the post-BRICS period and revealed a unidirectional causal relationship between trade liberalization and economic growth. The results also indicated a positive association between trade openness and economic development, implying that openness engendered growth and facilitated broader development outcomes in South Africa.

Denwi, Ikue & Onodjaefe (2022) empirically examined the relationship between trade liberalization policy and economic growth of 42 African countries from 1995 to 2018. Dynamic panel data sourced from Penn World Tables (PWT), International Monetary Fund (IMF) database and World Development Indicators (WDI) of World Bank were utilized for the study. The estimated model specified trade openness (TOP), financial system efficiency (FSE), domestic price stability (INFR), natural resources' rent (NTRR), national debt (DEBT), gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), population growth (POP), human capital index (HCI) and institutional quality (INSTQ) as independent variables while annual per capita income (APCI) was the dependent variable. Pooled Mean Group (PMG) technique was employed in estimating the parameters of the model. Empirical findings revealed that trade liberalization policy exerted a positive impact on economic growth of African countries up to a certain threshold, beyond which it began to cause the economy to under-heat. The study recommended among others, the

promulgation of competitive policies and debt obtained should be channeled to priority infrastructures capable of increasing the manufacturing base of countries in Africa. Gideon (2020) empirically investigated the impact of trade liberalization on economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. Annual panel data sourced from World Development Indicator (WDI) and Penn World Table (PWT) was used for the study. The estimated model specified real gross domestic product (RGDP) as the dependent variable while exports (EXP), imports (IMP), exchange rate (EXGR) and interest rate (INTR) were the explanatory variables of interest. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique was employed in estimating the parameters of the model. Empirical findings showed that exports and imports exhibited statistically significant positive impacts on economic growth of the Sub-Saharan Africa countries studied. On the other hand, exchange rate and interest rate exerted statically significant negative relationships with economic growth of these economies.

Umar et al. (2020) empirically investigated the nexus between trade liberalization and economic growth in Asian Tigers' economies by applying annually panel data regression approach between the periods 1960 to 2014. Secondary data obtained from the Penn World Table (PWT) was used for the study. Real gross domestic product (RGDP) was specified as the endogenous variable while human capital index (LHCI), export price (LEX) and import price (LIM) were the exogenous variables of interest. Empirical results showed that trade liberalization exerted a statistically significant positive impact on Asian tigers' economic growth for the studied period. The study recommended that policies relating to foreign direct investment must be reviewed to protect local industries.

Ijirshar (2020) assessed the impact of trade openness on economic growth among ECOWAS countries over the period 1975 to 2017. Secondary panel data obtained from World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) was utilized for the study. Pooled mean Group (PMG) and Mean Group (MG) estimators (Dynamic panel data estimators) were employed in estimating the parameters of the model. The estimated model was developed using the augmented version of the Solow-Swan model that incorporated human capital. Real gross domestic product per capita (RGDPPC) was specified as the dependent variable while trade openness, labour force, gross fixed capital formation, foreign direct investment, government expenditure and exchange rate were the explanatory variables of interest. Empirical findings showed that trade openness had highly significant positive impact on growth of ECOWAS member countries in the long run.³⁷ Kemal & Turgay (2020) empirically examined the long term and short-term relationships between trade liberalization and economic growth for 13 transition countries in Europe from 1995 to 2016. The exogenous variables of interest were export (EXPT), import (IMPT), gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), foreign direct investment (FDI) and human capital (HC) while the endogenous variable was gross domestic product (GDP). Panel unit root test, Swamy panel homogeneity test, panel cointegration test, Granger panel causality test, Westerlund Error Correction Model (WECM) panel cointegration

and PDOLS estimating techniques were employed for the study. Empirical results indicated that trade liberalization had a statistically significant positive impact on economic growth in both the short run and long run in the countries studied.

Methodology

This paper employed panel data collected from World Development Indicators (WDI) to analyze the effect of trade liberalization on economic growth of forty-five (45) Sub-Saharan African countries between 2000 and 2022. The forty-five (45) selected SSA countries are: Burundi, Djibouti, Ethiopia, Eritrea, Kenya, Rwanda, Kenya, Somalia, Tanzania, Uganda (Eastern Africa). The Western Africa sub-region includes the following countries: Benin, Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Cote D'Ivoire, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Mauritania, Nigeria, Niger, Senegal, Sierra-Leone and Togo. The Southern Africa countries included in the list are Angola, Botswana, Lesotho, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Swaziland, Zambia and Zimbabwe while the Central Africa countries include Burundi, Angola, Cameroun, Central Africa Republic, Chad, the Republic of Congo, Democratic Republic of Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Rwanda, and Sao Tome & Principe. The justifications for selecting or choosing Sub-Saharan African region for this study are numerous. First, nearly all the SSA countries are classified as developing countries that depend on exportation of natural resources, especially oil and mineral resources, for their incomes by many international organizations such as World Bank (WB), International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Trade Organization (WTO) and United Nations Organization (UNO). Second, the countries in this region have similar livelihood systems and share colonial experience. Third, the region is characterized by major geographical features such as tropical rainforests, savannahs, the Sahel region, and the Sahara Desert. Large lakes, mountains, rivers, and volcanoes are also found in Sub-Saharan Africa. Fourth, Sub-Sahara Africa region is the part of Africa that is located south of the Sahara Desert. This area is distinguished from the northern region of Africa by the Sahara itself.

The model specified for this paper will be estimated using the Pooled Ordinary Least Square (POLS), Panel Fixed Effect Model (PFEM) and Generalized Method of Moments (GMM). For the Pooled Ordinary Least Square (POLS), its estimating equation is a standard linear regression model, in which the dependent variable (Y_{it}) is regressed on the independent variables (X_{it}) for everyone i at time t . This equation can be expressed mathematically as follows:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

where:

Y_{it} = the dependent variable for individual i at time t

X_{it} = the independent variable for individual i at time t ,

β_0 and β_1 are the coefficients that are to be estimated

ϵ_{it} is the error term

In the case of Panel Fixed Effect Model (PFEM), its estimating equation captures fixed effects to each individual (each country in this case) so as to analyze the individual-specific effects. The PFEM equation can be written as:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 X_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

where:

α_i = the fixed effect for individual i ; while other variables are the same as in the POLS equation. And for the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM), its estimating technique involves specification of moment conditions that are based on data generating process. The GMM estimator attempts to minimize the difference between the sample moments and the population moments. The equation can be expressed as:

$$E[g(W_i, \theta)] = 0 \quad (3)$$

where:

$g(W_i, \theta)$ represents the moment condition function

θ constitute the parameters to be estimated

W_i is the data for individual (country) i

Note that these estimating equations (1,2&3) explain how POLS, PFEM, and GMM are formulated towards estimating the relationships among the variables of interest in the panel data analysis, with each of them addressing different aspects of the data structure and their underlying assumptions.

Data Description, Sources and Measurements

This study investigates the relationship between trade liberalization and economic growth of Sub-Saharan African countries. Cross-sectional and time series data spanning from 2000 to 2021 are used for the analysis. The annual secondary data is sourced from the World Development Indicator (WDI, 2022). The variables in this study are described and measured as presented in the table below.

Table 1 Description and Measures of Variables

Variable	Description	Expected Signs
GDPGR	Gross domestic product growth (annual %)	$Y_{it} > / < 0$
GCF	Gross capital formation (% of GDP)	Positive
LABF	Total labour force	Positive
TLIB	Merchandise trade (% of GDP)	Positive
NFDI	Net foreign direct investment (BOP, Current US\$)	Positive
TPOP	Annual total population	Positive
INFR	Inflation rate, CPI	Positive/Negative

Source: World Development Indicators (WDI), 2022

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Obs.
GDP	2.94	5.74	3.95	7.34	4.65	1024
TLIB	56.21	175.38	7.806	29.161	1.21	1035
NFDI	6.10	4.07	-7.40	1.87	10.49	1032
GCF	22.43	76.78	0.00	9.57	0.94	916
LABF	7811935	73389347	44913.00	11375984	2.86	1012
INFR	13.05	2630.12	-22.93	87.28	26.85	1024

Source: Authors' computation using E-views version 9

In Table 2 above, the mean value of trade liberalization is 56.21 for the region during the period of study. This shows that there is a moderate degree of trade liberalization by SSA countries with the rest of the world which could affect economic growth in the region positively. The average mean values of gross fixed capital formation and net foreign direct investment are 22.43 and 6.10 respectively. In addition, the skewness value of trade liberalization which measures the asymmetry or distortion of symmetric distribution is 1.21 indicating that the distribution of data is moderately and positively skewed. The maximum for SSA region lies at 175.38 (for Congo Republic in 2016) and minimum value is 7.806 (for Congo Democratic in 2000). The descriptive statistics also revealed that the mean value of economic growth proxied by GDP stands at 2.94 percent indicating low output of goods and services in the SSA region during the period of study. The standard deviation value of 7.34 indicates that the data points are not clustered around the mean. The skewness value of 4.65 indicates the direction and relative magnitude of a distribution's deviation from the normal distribution. As far as economic growth is concerned, the data is positively skewed.

Model Specification

The study adopted the empirical framework of the augmented neoclassical growth theory as suggested by Mankiw, Romer and Weil (1992) that incorporated human capital. Thus, the Cobb-Douglas production function is stated as:

$$Y_{it} = A_{it} f (K_{it}^{\alpha} T_{it}^{\beta} L_{it}^{1-\alpha-\beta})$$

(4) where

Y_{it} = Real gross domestic output in country i at time t

K_{it} = Stock of physical capital in country i at time t

L_{it} = Labour population growth in country i at time t

T_{it} = Trade liberalization in country i at time t. t is time dimension and i represents cross sections. $0 < \alpha < 1$ is the elasticity of output with respect to capital and elasticity of output with respect to labour. A_{it} connotes labour knowledge or augmenting technology.

The theoretical foundation for this specification is found in the Solow growth model and its extension; the endogenous growth theory which is an improvement of the Solow growth model.

According to endogenous growth model, economic growth is influenced by several other economic variables aside from labour and capital. It is assumed that economic growth (RGDP) is influenced by gross capital formation (GCF), labour force (LABF), trade liberalization (TLIB), net foreign direct investment (NFDI), total population growth (TPOP) and inflation rate (INFR). The above dependent and independent variables can be expressed in mathematical form as shown below:
 $RGDP = F(GFCF, LABF, TLIB, NFDI, TPOP, INFR) \quad (5)$

The econometric transformation of the mathematical form of equation (2) is given below: $GRGDP_{it} = \beta_{1i} + \beta_{2i}GCF_{it} + \beta_{3i}LABF_{it} + \beta_{4i}TLIB_{it} + \beta_{5i}NFDI_{it} + \beta_{6i}TPOP_{it} + \beta_{7i}INFR_{it} + E_{it} \quad (6)$ In terms of a-priori theoretical expectation about the signs and size of the exogenous variables of the model, the parameter estimates $\beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ and β_6 are expected to exhibit positive relationships with economic growth while β_7 should have negative sign.

Discussion of Findings

Table 3
Panel Ordinary Least Squares Estimated Result
Dependent Variable: GDP
Method: Panel Least Squares

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
GDP(-1)	0.777817***	0.015662	49.66405	0.0000
TLIB	55768052.09*	42848352	1.301522	0.1934
NFDI	3.165830***	0.454482	6.965801	0.0000
GFCF	-2.329912*	94278656	-2.456538	0.0142
LABF	78.32237	375.8779	0.208372	0.8350
TPOP	328.1426**	157.5520	2.082757	0.0376
INFR	1507544	7925659	0.190211	0.8492
C	-4.674828	2.51E-09	-0.186309	0.8522
R-squared = 0.856191	Adjusted R-squared = 0.854639	F-statistic= 551.7058 Pro(Fstatistic)=0.000000	DW = 0.615397	

Note: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$ signify significance of the estimated parameters and F-statistics. **Source:** Authors' computation using E-views version 9

The results of the pooled OLS showed that: (a) the coefficient of the lagged dependent variable (RGDP(-1)) is statistically significant and considered to be the upper bond estimate; (b) the trade liberalization predictor influenced economic growth positively and significantly; (c) net foreign direct investment and total population have statistically significant positive relationships with economic growth; (d) gross fixed capital formation exerted a statistically significant negative relationship with economic growth; (e) labour force is the only predictor variable that influenced economic growth positively and insignificantly; (f) the R-squared

value of 0.856191 indicates that eighty-five percent of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables in the model. Due to the major weaknesses of pooled OLS approach which are: (i) the presence of unobserved individual-specific effects that are correlated with the independent variables, making pooled OLS suffer from omitted variable bias; (ii) the pooled OLS estimates will be biased and inconsistent, as the model fails to control for the unobserved heterogeneity.

Table 4
Panel Fixed Effect Model Result
Dependent Variable: GDP
Method: Panel Least Squares

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
GDP(-1)	0.585074***	0.026601	21.99449	0.0000
TLIB	51714299	44883626	1.152186	0.2496
NFDI	1.757985***	0.308998	5.689290	0.0000
GFCF	-1.357876*	91021304	-1.482936	0.1385
LABF	-2651.320***	701.56401	-3.779156	0.0002
TPOP	2544.374***	291.5545	8.726926	0.0000
INFR	-18781860***	5301709	-3.542605	0.0004
C	-1.459224***	2.91E-09	-4.984471	0.0000
R-squared = 0.945169	Adjusted R-squared = 0.941490	R-squared =	F-statistic = 256.9416 Pro(F-statistic) = 0.000000***	DW = 1.12414

Note: ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.10 signify significance of the estimated parameters and F-statistics. **Source:** Authors' computation using E-views version 9.

The parameter estimates of the panel fixed effects results are reported below due to the weaknesses of pooled OLS methodology enumerated above. Empirical findings of the panel fixed effects estimates showed that: (a) the coefficient of the lagged dependent variable (RGDP(-1)) is statistically significant and regarded as the lower bond estimate; (b) trade liberalization has positive but insignificant effect on economic growth; (c) net foreign direct investment and population are predictors that influenced economic growth positively and significantly; (d) gross fixed capital formation, labour force and inflation rate have statistically significant negative relationships with economic growth; (e) the R-squared value of 0.945169 indicates that ninety-four percent of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables in the model. As a result of the primary limitation of fixed effects model which is unobserved heterogeneity due to unmeasured characteristics that do vary overtime, the two-step difference generalized method of moment estimator will be employed for this model

Table 5

Dependent Variable: GDP

Method: Two-Step Difference Generalized Method of Moments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
GDP(-1)	0.573317***	0.000893	641.8738	0.0000
TLIB	2.365332***	13829649	17.03249	0.0000
NFDI	1.880233***	0.016526	113.7734	0.0000
GFCF	-3.983894***	35233275	-11.29157	0.0000
LABF	-4137.808***	94.31298	-43.87315	0.0000
TPOP	3407.562***	100.0694	34.05198	0.0000
INFR	11104110***	3016514	3.681106	0.0002
AR (1)	-0.480478	-	-	0.3546
AR (2)	-0.326417	-	-	0.5528
Hanse J-statistic	36.73328	-	-	-
Prob (J-statistic)		-	-	0.299896
Instruments	10	Instrument Rank= 42		
Countries	45	-	-	-
Observations	788	-	-	-

Note: ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.10. The values in the bracket signify significance of (a) estimated parameters and (b) failure to reject the null hypotheses of: (i) no autocorrelation in the AR(1) and AR(2) tests and (ii) the validity of the instruments in the Hansen over-identifying restriction OIR test

Source: Authors' computation using E-views version 9

Table 5 above presents the empirical results of the relationship between trade liberalization and economic growth in SSA countries. The estimated results of Two-Step Difference Generalized Method of Moments (TSDGMM) for the relationship between these two variables are presented, reported and interpreted below.

From the table, the coefficient of the lagged dependent variable of difference GMM (0.653317) lies in-between the upper bond estimate (0.777817) and the lower bond estimate (0.585074) of the pooled OLS and panel fixed effects approach, signifying that the two-step difference GMM does not suffer from downward bias ($0.585074 < 0.653317 < 0.777817$). The estimated results of the two-step difference GMM revealed that trade liberalization has a positive and statistically significant relationship with economic growth in SSA countries, ceteris paribus. The coefficient of the regressor is in line with a-priori theoretical expectation about the sign and size of the magnitude. A one percent increase in trade liberalization resulted in 2.365335 percent corresponding rise in economic growth. This result is in line with the findings of some previous empirical studies (such as B. Dragusha et al. 2023⁴; O. O. Adeoye, 2023⁵; A. K. A. Ahmed & J. S. Hussein, 2023⁶; U. E. Ita et al. 2023⁷; S. Mohammed et al. 2022⁸; M. Ogundipe & A. Adenekan, 2022⁹; I. U. Duru, 2021¹⁰; and O. A. Gideon, 2020¹¹). The implication of this result is that the elimination of tariff and non-tariff barriers from the free flow of goods and services between SSA countries and the rest of the world has paved way

for increased efficiency and specialization, access to international markets, attraction of foreign direct investment, increased competition and innovation, lower prices and increased consumption, creation of jobs, reduced poverty, integration into the global economy and encouraging domestic firms to become more competitive.

Furthermore, the estimated results also reveal that net foreign direct investment (NFDI) exerts a statistically significant positive relationship with economic growth, other things remain equal. A one unit change in net foreign direct investment results in 1.880233 units change in economic growth. This result is in line with theoretical expectation and implies that net foreign direct investment positively impacts economic growth in Sub-Saharan African countries by fostering capital formation and infrastructure development, technology transfer, increasing productivity, increased competitiveness and innovation, job creation and human capital development, and boosting exports. Moreover, population (POP) has a positive and significant impact on economic growth in SSA countries, *ceteris paribus*. This result is consistent with theoretical expectation and can be interpreted as a one unit increase in population would result in 3407.562 units rise in economic growth. The implication of this result is that a larger, younger, and educated population in Sub-Saharan Africa can positively drive economic growth by increasing the workforce, creating demand for goods and services, and fostering innovation and technological advancement, ultimately boosting productivity and economic expansion but only if coupled with investments in education and infrastructure.

Conversely, government capital formation (GCF) and labour force (LABF) have statistically significant negative relationships with economic growth, all other factors remain constant. This result can be interpreted as a one percent increase in government fixed capital formation and labour force would bring about 3.983894 and 4137.808 corresponding percentage reductions in economic growth. Regarding the negative coefficient of government capital formation, this implies that government capital formation negatively affects economic growth in SSA countries due to factors like poor project selection, corruption and mismanagement, lack of private sector participation, poor institutional capacity, unfavorable macroeconomic conditions, and inefficient implementation, leading to wasted resources and reduced long-term productivity. Furthermore, the negative relationship between labour force and economic growth is inconsistent with a-priori theoretical expectation. The implication is that a large proportion of the workforce are aged, unproductive and dependent on the small working class population. It is also associated with slower economic growth through a range of channels including a lower worker-to population ratio.

Lastly, inflation rate (INFR) has a statistically significant positive association with economic growth contrary to economic theory. Based on the estimated results, trade liberalization has positive impact on economic growth of SSA countries, *ceteris paribus*. The Hansen J-statistical probability value of 0.299896 which is higher than 5 percent (0.05) suggests that the over identifying restrictions imposed on the two-step difference generalized

method of moments are valid. In addition, the Arellano and Bond first order serial correlation test AR(1) whose probability value is estimated at (0.3546) and second order serial correlation test with the probability value of (0.5528) conducted indicates the absence of first order and second-order serial correlations in the first differenced errors because the probability values of their chi-square statistics are greater than 0.05(5%). This suggests that the residuals are not serially correlated. The implication of this is that the two-step difference generalized method of moments is an accurate and consistent estimator.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Empirical evidence from the econometric results revealed that there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between trade liberalization and economic growth in SSA countries. The implication of this result is that reducing trade barriers leads to increased economic activity and prosperity. For simplicity's sake, exports, net foreign direct investment, total population and inflation rate influenced economic growth positively while imports, gross capital formation and labour force impacted economic growth negatively. Based on the outcomes of the estimated models for this study, the following recommendations are made.

a) **Strengthening Domestic Institutions and Governance:** SSA countries need to strengthen their domestic institutions, particularly those related to governance and contract enforcement. There should be streamlining processes like import and export licensing and adopting uniform, reasonably low tariff rates can improve transparency, reduce rent-seeking, and minimize corruption.

b) **Massive Investment in Infrastructure and Human Capital Development:** Investments in infrastructure are germane for supporting trade and enhancing overall economic performance. Also, investments in education and re-skilling workers are necessary, particularly in manufacturing, to improve competitiveness in the face of increased import competition.

c) **Implementation of Complementary Policies:** Government of SSA countries should implement supportive policies that address potential challenges and enhance the benefits of trade liberalization. This includes developing more integrated regional trade systems that can boost resilience and enhance global competitiveness, diversifying export bases away from traditional commodities and developing new products can lead to more sustainable growth.

d) **Stabilization of Macroeconomic Policies:** Implementation of macroeconomic stability is essential for supporting sustainable, long-term growth and maximizing the benefits of trade liberalization. The key elements include consistent and transparent policy implementation, strong institutional frameworks, proactive responses to economic imbalances, and consideration of the economy's structural characteristics to foster resilience against shocks and promote long-term well-being.

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